

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1825 Max: 63.2786	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1258 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	
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In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No	In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No	Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 1134-1177	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:
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DEFINITION Round Fill	Covered by ☒ SU: 1189	Fills ☒ SU: 1259	Filled by ☐ SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☒ Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS ☒ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 60% sand 30%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☒ Cohesive
☒ Pottery R ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☐ Nails ☐ Marble ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Opus signinum ☒ Painted plaster R ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☒ Clay ☒ Sand ☒ Silt ☒ Pebbles (range) M (cobble-sized @ top of deposit) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☒ Animal bones R ☐ Human bones ☒ Animal teeth R ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)
			Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☒ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft
			Color ☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1189	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1259

OBSERVATIONS Not a lot of inclusions. Definitely a little more Excavated w/ trowel & spoon on sunny, temperate (for Gabii) day.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: NE corner of "Room II"
Shape: Rectangular with one rounded side

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): No slope
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) several cobble-sized rocks in top part of deposit (over lowest ashlar block)
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thicker S of wall
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight</p> <p>Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p> <p style="text-align: right;"> ☐ - Stone ☐ - 1173 ☐ - 1258 </p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

A hole was cut into 1173 & 1187, but was cut deeper into 1173 and later got filled. It could have been a posthole. I honestly have no idea what else it could have been.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CAK	on	27-7-10
Revised by	CM7	on	27.07.2010
PDFd by	JTM	on	28/7/2010
Entered by		on	